

**MAIN THEMES AND IDEAS RAISED IN THE NOVEL OF “AND THE
MOUNTAINS ECHOED”**

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Annotation: The following article is about the novel “And The Mountains Echoed” by Khaled Hossieni and analyzes the main features of the novel. The main topic raised in the novel, situation in Afghanistan in that time, how was Talibans, how they tackle, the family problems especially between siblings.

Key words: structure, style, symbols, conflict, "And The Mountains Echoed", Khaled Hosseini, Farm, City, The War and Homs, siblings, family, kindness.

“And The Mountains Echoed”’s written by Afghan-American poet Khaled Hosseini published in 2013 by Riverhead Books. “And the Mountains Echoed” cost \$28.95 in the US and £14.99 in the UK when it was first published in hardcover. To promote the book, Hosseini undertook a five-week tour that visited 41 cities in America. Plans to translate “And the Mountains Echoed” into 40 languages, including Malay and Icelandic, were confirmed in October 2013. Each of the nine chapters is recounted from a different character's perspective, and each narrative links to the others. Khaled Hosseini choose to portray the story in this fragmented and flowing way. Wendy Smith, a critic for the Los Angeles Times, linked this genre to the timeless One Thousand and One Nights. Before the book's publication, Hosseini stated: "Family is always pulled to me as a reoccurring key theme of my writing." My earlier books primarily dealt with motherhood and fatherhood. This book presents its story via the lens of sibling relationships, a topic that is refracted through the lives of various pairs of brothers and sisters, in contrast to “A Thousand Splendid Suns” and “The Kite Runner,” which concentrated on the dynamic between

mothers and daughters and fathers and sons, respectively.¹ And the Mountains Echoed is mostly about love, family, and pain, according to Khaled Hosseini. Abdullah and Pari's separation is the book's heart,² according to the author. Both later turn into "victims of time": Pari is younger and is able to move on from her brother's death, whereas Abdullah, who is older and remembers Pari, gas well as he always cry for the most of his life because of his sister. When Pari knows that she was adopted and that she has a brother named Abdullah toward the end of the book, she searches for him there but she finds that he has Alzheimer's disease and he has forgotten about her. From this context the question of whether memory is a blessing something that protects all the things you hold dear or a curse something that forces you to relive the most upsetting moments of your life, the toil, the effort, and the tragedies has been brought up numerous times, according to Hosseini. Because of this, "And The Mountains Echoed" is kind of like a fairy tale turned on its head,³ according to author. At their core, all three of my books are, in my opinion, love stories, but not in the conventional sense of a man and a woman falling in love, rather than they are the tales of characters falling in love with one another in unexpected places. Therefore, it is always these extreme interactions that develop in unexpected ways.

According to a report by Amnesty International USA director Rafia Zakaria, the themes of regret and thankfulness are also so common. She gave the background of Parwana is stepmother of Abdullah, Pari, and Masooma, as an illustration: "A moving narrative about a plain twin who, in one act of revenge, pushed her attractive sister off a swing and suffered the consequences for the rest of her life is revealed. The sister, who was engaged to be married to a guy both sisters adore, is rendered permanently disabled, and both sisters serve their time while the healthy sister cares

¹ Kakutani, Michiko(may 20,2013) "Siblings Haunted by the Past, and by Afghanistan's Cycle of Misery". The New York Times. Retrieved August 24,2013.

² Siblings Separation Haunts in "Kite Runner" Author's Latest. NPR. May 19, 2013. retrieved September 5, 2013.

³ Hoby, Hermione (May 31, 2013). Khaled Hosseini: If I could go back now, I'd take The Kite Runner apart. The Guardian. Retrieved September 8, 2013.

for the other and is internally torn apart by the realization that she is to blame for their unfortunate circumstances." the plot of this novel is begin in 1952 with a guy telling his son and daughter a tale about a villager who was forced to surrender his adored youngest child to a wicked stepmother or devil. Saboor is often authoritarian and uncommunicative, but occasionally he surprises Abdullah. Abdullah was 10, and Pari was 3 years old, with stories of magical creatures and far-off locations that briefly free their father's imagination, which has been stifled by years of arduous labor and poverty. When they get to Kabul, the kids discover the horrifying importance of this particular story. Their Uncle Nabi has made arrangements for Suleiman and Nila Wahdati, his affluent, childless employers, to adopt Pari. The screaming, terrified girl is quickly taken away. Her distraught brother is brought back to their hamlet, but his father forbids him from expressing any emotion. However, Saboor is also broken by this desertion, he never shares another tale. The way that each following story develops from the one before it is reminiscent of the traditional structure of "A Thousand and One Nights". The magic of storytelling imbues the book with a harsh kind of confidence, a belief that even if people can't necessarily wring happiness from a hard world, they may at least gain understanding.

This is true even though the novel is realistic in form and frequently gloomy in subject matter. As numerous, closely interwoven narrators develop their individual stories within the greater drama of Afghanistan's painful experience, the chronology becomes jumbled and disorderly. Nila leaves for Paris in order to rescue herself and Pari from the patriarchal limitations placed on Afghan women after Suleiman has a stroke in 1955. When we see them again in 1974, Pari's background has been erased thanks to Nila's falsehoods, she was brought up believing she is this drunken, angered woman's biological daughter and has forgotten about her missing brother. However, the lack of something, or someone, crucial to her own existence, has plagued Pari her whole life. As seen in his testimony via the harm done to the Wahdati home by rockets and looters, Nabi takes care of Suleiman throughout the

1990s civil war and the Taliban's ruthless regime. Nabi accepts the house as a gift from Suleiman after he passes away and leaves it to him as a residence for medical professionals caring for hurt children once the Taliban have been driven out. Idris and Timur cousins who grew up next door to this structure, travel to Kabul to reclaim the home their family left behind during the Soviet invasion. After returning to San Francisco, where a brief scene reintroduces Abdullah, now the gray-haired owner of a kebab business with a daughter named Pari, the gap between these wealthy Afghan-Americans and those who were unable to flee is shockingly shown.

In the California sun, promises to arrange surgery for an Afghan boy who had been damaged by a psychotic relative progressively fade, but they are ultimately kept by an unexpected source. The reader is taken back to the only chapter that is equally unsettling and excellent as this analysis of moral weakness. It takes place in the village where Pari and Abdullah were born. A young kid is slowly made aware by Hosseini that his beloved father is actually a war criminal who has built a stately home on Saboor's property and murdered the person who had the rightful ownership of it, not the village's sponsor. The novel's more prevalent and forgiving portraits of characters who are hampered by circumstance and make mistakes are contrasted with these two gloomy occurrences. As seen in the heartbreaking last chapter written by Abdullah's daughter Pari in 2010, mistakes have unavoidable bad outcome. The harm done by fate and chance cannot be repaired by rediscovering a stolen past. "And the Mountains Echoed" is extremely depressing but also joyful with love, the steadfast relationship between a brother and sister, the tense but steadfast relationship between cousins, the quiet closeness of a master and servant who become friends, the dedication of a doctor and nurse to the victims of war. Hosseini ends the book with an image from a dream, a memory of past bliss made all the more valuable in hindsight because we are aware of how fleeting it is, to emphasize the significance and contingency of love. Main characters from "And The Mountains Echoed" are Abdullah and his sister Pari. Abdullah - is an Afghan and was born and

raised in the made-up community of Shadbagh. Following his father Saboor's decision to sell his younger sister to Mr. and Mrs. Whadati, a wealthy couple in Kabul, he decides to escape Afghanistan and finally makes his way to Pakistan and the United States. He had a kid there and names her after his sister before opening an Afghan restaurant. Abdullah is given an Alzheimer's diagnosis when his wife passes away, and even after being reunited with his sister, he is unable to recall her. Pari - the younger sister of Abdullah, is sold to the affluent Wahdati couple in Kabul by her father Saboor when she is three years old. She and Abdullah are seen to have an extraordinarily strong relationship in their early years, but after she is adopted, she forgets both of them and the rest of her biological family. After her adoptive father suffers a stroke, she spends her teenage and adult years in France. Years later, she learns of her past thanks to a letter from her uncle Nabi, who had arranged for her to be sold as a child. As a result of his Alzheimer's, Abdullah is unable to recall her when they are ultimately reunited.

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